

Environmental Perspective on Clothing Article Disposal Practices of Households in Port Harcourt Metropolis: Implication for sustainable environmental development

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Abstract

This study determined environmental perspective on clothing articles disposal practices of households in Port Harcourt metropolis. Specifically, it identified reasons for clothing article disposal; clothing articles disposal practices of households; negative effect of clothing article waste disposal practices and sustainable practices for efficient clothing article waste disposal in Port Harcourt metropolis. A survey design was used for the study. Population was made up of all households in Port Harcourt metropolis. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 300 residents. Sampling occur in four stages. Random sampling technique and purposive sampling techniques were utilized to select the target sample. Questionnaire titled "environmental perspective on clothing article disposal of household Questionnaire" (EPCADHQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire has four-point responses categories of Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree and strongly disagree. The questionnaire consists of 38 items developed from the reviewed literature. The instrument was validated by three experts in the faculty of Vocational and Technical Education, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. To determine the consistence of the instrument, the instrument was trial tested and Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.79 was obtained. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. Major findings revealed ten reasons for clothing article disposal. These include wear and tear (4.00 ± 0.00); change in body size, weight and shape (4.00 ± 0.00); poor fit (4.00 ± 0.00); colours fading (3.95) and clothing article being out of fashion (3.80). Eight clothing article waste disposal practices of households include burning waste clothing articles (3.84 \pm 0.83), giving to friends and family members (3.80), throwing away waste clothing articles in dust bin (3.76); donating to charity organization (3.50) and burying in pits (2.63; Findings also revealed that none of the respondents had sold nor dispose of their clothing articles to companies for recycling. Seven negative effects of clothing article waste disposal practices include blockage of drainage (4.00), destroying aesthetic beauty of the environment (3.97), water pollution (3.86) and air pollution (3.74). Twelve sustainable practices for efficient clothing article waste disposal include buying durable and quality clothing (4.00), buying only clothing articles needed (4.00), repurposing clothing articles (3.97), repair (3.76), refashion (3.74), recycle (3.65) and reuse (3.61 \pm 0.02) of clothing articles. Recommendations for households in Port Harcourt metropolis to adopt sustainable clothing article waste disposal practices as well as stake holders and government to collaborate and set up clothing recycling plant in Port Harcourt was made.

Keywords: Environmental perspective, Clothing, Clothing Disposal, Practices, Households

Introduction

The society globally is faced with change in Earth's climate. This change environmental issues that have induced a resulting from environmental and social

aspect have resulted to negative effects such as global warming, deterioration of ecosystems and biodiversity, social issues, which has also led to changes in production and consumption behaviors that are no longer sustainable (Mezghenni and Zouaris, 2016). Clothing article consumption and waste disposal has been on the increase due to fast fashion which motivates consumers to buy more clothing articles. Fast fashion retailing is leading consumers towards an increased rate of purchasing and the trend to keep clothing for shorter time with the resulting rise in clothing disposal. Moreover, the short lifecycles of clothing articles due to rapid fashion cycles and increased buying power of consumers in urban areas has resulted in significant amount of post-consumer clothing articles waste in the form of used clothing articles.

Postconsumer waste consists of any types of garments or household articles made from fabricated textiles that the owner no longer needs and decides to discard (Coskun and Basaran, 2019). Consumers may discard these articles when they are worn out, damaged, outgrown, or out of fashion. The volume of postconsumer waste is very large and is comparable with the rate of fiber consumption (Wang 2010). Although a part of this postconsumer waste is given to charities or passed on to friends and family members, most of it is deposited into the trash and ends up in municipal landfills (Hawley 2006). The amount of postconsumer waste is very large in comparison with other waste types (Wang 2010). It has been estimated that the volumes of postconsumer textile waste that go to landfills are 10.5 million tons per year in the USA, 350,000 tons per year in the UK, and 287,000 tons per year in Turkey (Karaosman, Morales-Alonso and Brun, 2016). According to Ajila (2019; Bakere, 2019) the quantity of solid waste generated per annum in Nigeria assumed 32 million tons, out of which only 20 – 30% is collected. Since an item of clothing has approximately a 2-year lifetime, postconsumer waste should be collected for acquisition purposes ((Karaosman, Morales-Alonso and Brun, 2016)).

One of the issues Nigeria and the world at large are facing is the issue of waste disposal (Efe, 2013; Freduah, 2016). The quantity of waste that is generated and sends to landfills on a daily basis is at a great cost to the environment. The increased waste caused by clothing article disposal practices, and the environmental impact of these activities, has become increasingly harmful (Efe, 2013; Lekan, Hezekiah and Omoighele, 2018). Disposal of solid waste is the least favored waste management method, in which the last destination of waste is a landfill site (Lekan, Hezekiah and Omoighele, 2018). Countries try to manage waste with other options and many organizations in waste management around the world are working to raise awareness of textile waste. According to (Coskuma and Basaran, 2019) efficient waste management for sustainable development involves the 3R (reduce, reuse and recycle). This strategy is also integrated in the United Nations Sustainable development goals as the target of goal 12 is to ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns by aiming to substantially reduce waste generation through the 3R by 2030 (United Nations, 2018).

This 3R is also used for textile waste management sustainable practices (Newell, 2015). In textile waste, repair of clothing articles is considered in the reduce stage as one of the components of this hierarchy. Repair of clothing articles involves mending clothing articles so it is used for its original purpose. The second principle in the 3R is reuse. This focusses on using an item again to prolong its life. Repurposing (to change a clothing article so that it can be used for a different purpose); refashioning (to alter clothing article for reuse) and redesigning (recontextualizing wasted clothing articles without changing its form) of clothing articles is considered as one of the components of this hierarchy (Dissanayak, Perera and Wanniarachch). The final R in the waste hierarchy is recycle. Textile recycling is the reprocessing of pre or post-consumer textile waste for use in new textiles or non-textile products. The purpose of this management sustainable practices is

to provide maximum benefits by prolonging the life of the products thereby reducing waste (Thompson, 2017). However, there is still a huge amount of waste that ends its life in a landfill even though it could be reduced, reused or recycled (Bhuiya 2017).

In landfills, synthetic textile waste does not decompose, while woolen garments do decompose but produce methane and carbon dioxide gases, contributing to global warming (Strähle and Hauk 2017). With the disposal of waste in landfills, it must be noted that methane emissions are more harmful than carbon dioxide emissions (Sotayo, green and Turvey, 2015). Also, incineration of clothing items multiplies climate impact of the product by generating further emissions and air pollutants that can harm human health. In Port Harcourt metropolis, postconsumer wastes are being burnt, buried and thrown away in dustbins most times which ends up in landfills. These practices concerning clothing articles waste disposal has major implications on households in Port Harcourt metropolis regarding environmental concerns. Hence the significance of the present study on environmental perspective on clothing article disposal practices of households in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the reasons for clothing article disposal in Port Harcourt metropolis?
2. What are the clothing article disposal practices of households in Port Harcourt metropolis?
3. What are the negative effects of clothing articles waste disposal practices on households in Port Harcourt metropolis?
4. What are the sustainable practices for efficient clothing article waste disposal in Port Harcourt metropolis?

Methodology

Design of the Study

The design of the study was a survey.

Area of the Study: The study was carried out in Port Harcourt metropolis. Port

Harcourt is the capital of Rivers State. It has a population of about 5, 198, 716 (National Population Commission, 2006). It is densely populated with different social strata of households (High income, middle income and low-income households).

Population for the Study

The population for this study was made up of all households in Port Harcourt metropolis. Members of the households were the respondents. According to the 2011 population, approximately 638, 360 people reside in Port Harcourt (Port Harcourt (LGA) city population, 2011).

Sample and Sampling Technique

Sample size for this study was three (300) hundred households (300). Multistage sampling technique was used. Sampling occurred in four stages. In the first stage, 15 areas (Azuabie, Abuloma, Amadi-Ama, Borokiri, D-line, Diobu, Elekahia, New GRA, Nkpogu, Nkpolu, Ogbunabali, old GRA, Old Port Harcourt township, Rumuobiekwe, Rumuwoji,) were randomly selected from the 28 areas that made up Port Harcourt metropolis. In the second stage, two wards were randomly selected from the 15 selected areas making a total of 30 wards across. In the third stage, 2 longest streets were purposively selected from the 30 wards making a total of 60 streets. In the last stage, 5 households were purposively selected from the 60 longest street making a total of 300.

Instrument for Data Collection

A structured validated questionnaire was utilized for data collection. The questionnaire was developed for members of households and it was titled "Environmental perspective on clothing Article disposal of household questionnaire" (EPCADHQ). The questionnaire consisted of two sections. Section A sought for demographic characteristics of the respondents while section B generated items based on the purposes of the study. Section B also contained rating scale items as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

Method of Data Collection

300 copies of the questionnaire were administered by hand with the help of three research assistants. All the questionnaires were completed and returned on the spot. Proper guidance was given to respondents where necessary.

Method of Data Analysis: Data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. A mean of 2.50 and above was considered as positive and accepted while mean ratings that are less than 2.50 were regarded as negative and rejected.

Table 1: Mean Responses of households on Reasons for Clothing Articles Disposal

em No	Reasons for clothing article disposal	Mean	STD	Remark
1.	Wear and tear	4.000.00		Agree
2.	Changing body size, weight and shape	4.000.00		Agree
3.	Poor fit	4.000.00		Agree
4.	Out of fashion	3.800.25		Agree
5.	boredom	3.76	0.30	Agree
6.	lack of storage space	3.01	0.10	Agree
7.	changes in personal style	3.54	0.19	Agree
8.	individual life style	3.27	0.42	Agree
9.	new fashion	3.73	0.27	Agree
10.	colours fading	3.95	0.67	Agree

Table 1 showed that the mean value of 10 reasons for clothing articles disposal ranged from 4.00 - 3.01 and were above the cut -off point of 2.50 ($\bar{X} \hat{A} 2.50$). This indicated that households agreed that all the items in table

1 are reasons for disposing clothing articles. The standard deviation which ranges from 0.00 - 0.67 revealed the strength of the respondent.

Table 2: Mean Responses of Clothing Article Disposal Practices of Households

Item No	Clothing Articles Disposal Practices	Mean	STD	Remark
1.	I sell waste clothing articles for money	2.400.23		Disagree
2.	I donate waste clothing articles to charity organizations	3.500.29		Agree
3.	I give waste clothing articles to friends and family members	3.800.82		Agree
4.	I repurpose waste clothing articles for cleaning as rags	3.300.63		Agree
5.	I throw away waste clothing articles	3.76	0.72	Agree
6.	I burn waste clothing articles	3.84	0.83	Agree
7.	I bury waste clothing articles in pits	2.63	0.69	Agree
8.	I give out waste clothing articles for recycling	2.25	0.12	Disagree

Table 2 shows 8 clothing article disposal practices of homemakers. The table shows that 6 clothing disposal practices had highest mean agreed range from 3.84 - 3.30 and were above the cut -off point of 2.50 ($\bar{X} \hat{A} 2.50$) while 2 clothing articles disposal practices had mean disagreed range from

2.40 - 2.25 and were below the cut-off point of 2.50 ($\hat{A} 2.50$). This indicated that clothing waste disposal practices of households in Port Harcourt metropolis is not economical to households rather some of the practices like throwing away and burning of clothing articles has negative effects on households.

Table 3: Mean Responses of Households on Negative Effects of Clothing Articles waste Disposal Practices

Item No	Negative Effects of Clothing Articles waste disposal Practices on households	Mean	STD	Remark
1.	Blockage of drainages	4.000.00		Agree
2.	Flooding of residential areas	3.22	0.99	Agree
3.	Health hazards	3.59	1.02	Agree
4.	Air pollution	3.74	0.93	Agree
5.	Water pollution	3.86	0.92	Agree
6.	Destroys aesthetic beauty of the environment	3.97.	1.20	Agree
7.	Occurrence of diseases associated with poor sanitary conditions	3.54	1.15	Agree

Table 3 shows that the mean value of 7 negative effects of clothing articles disposal practices ranged from 4.00 – 3.22 and were above the cut -off point of 2.50 ($\bar{X} \bar{A} 2.50$). This indicated

that households agreed that all the items in table 3 are the negative effects of clothing article disposal practices on household in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Table 4: Mean Responses of Households on sustainable practices for Efficient Clothing Articles Waste Disposal

Item No	Sustainable practices for efficient clothing article waste disposal	Mean	STD	Remark
	Buy durable and quality clothing articles	4.00	0.00	Agree
1.	Buy only clothing articles needed	4.00	0.00	Agree
2.	Reuse clothing articles	3.61	0.02	Agree
3.	Repair clothing articles	3.74	0.93	Agree
4.	Refashion clothing articles	3.76	0.92	Agree
5.	Repurpose clothing articles	3.97	0.20	Agree
6.	Avoid impulsive buying of clothing articles	3.54	0.15	Agree
7.	Recycle clothing articles	3.65	0.92	Agree
8.	Buy clothes articles from sustainable brand	2.51	0.21	Agree
9.	Do not burn nor bury clothing articles	3.33	0.36	Agree
10.	Put clothing articles in recycle bin	2.98	0.18	Agree
11.	Do not throw clothing articles away in dust bins	3.49	0.64	Agree
12.	Rent clothes you will not wear for a long time	2.58	0.23	Agree

Table 4 shows that the mean value of 12 items on sustainable practices for efficient clothing articles disposal ranged from 4.00 – 2.51 and were above the cut -off point of 2.50 ($\bar{X} \bar{A} 2.50$). This indicated that all the 13 items are sustainable practices for efficient clothing articles disposal.

Discussion of Findings

This study focused on environmental perspective on clothing article disposal practices of households in Port Harcourt metropolis. The study found evidence that households in Port Harcourt metropolis dispose their waste clothing articles based on poor fit, out of fashion, wear and tear, changing body size, boredom, changes in personal style. This finding conforms with the findings of Laitala (2014); Bianchi and Birtwistle, 2010) who noted that clothing articles are disposed due to poor fit, boredom, out of fashion, wear and tear among others.

Bernades, Marques, Ferreira and Nogueira (2019) also noted that clothing articles are discarded or disposed when they become obsolete and are no longer in use mainly because of physical features of the products such as functionality, quality, psychological and social aspect such as fashion trends, individual life style and desires .

Research question two showed clothing article waste disposal practices of Households. These practices included donating clothing articles to charity organization, throwing away clothing articles, burning waste clothing articles, burying clothing waste articles, repurposing waste clothing article among others. This finding is inconsonance with that of Omole, Isiorh and Ndambuki (2019) who noted that commonly practiced disposal methods in Nigeria

includes burying, open air burning and open dumping. These practices the author added are ineffective and detrimental to public health and environment. Bernades, Marques, Ferreira and Nogueira (2019) also noted that consumers of clothing articles dispose of clothing articles by donating to families and friends, throwing away due to stains, tears or other damages and do not consider fixing them. The findings also revealed that households in Port Harcourt metropolis do not sell nor recycle waste clothing articles. This may be as a result of lack of store or organization in Port Harcourt metropolis to which they can sell to for recycling. Sonye and Adeniji (2017) noted that the recycling base of solid textile waste in Port Harcourt is weak as there is no recycling of textile waste as it is practiced in developed countries.

The finding of the study in relation to research question three revealed the negative effects of clothing articles waste disposal practices of households. These negative effects on households includes blockage of drainages, flooding of residential areas, health hazards, air pollution, water pollution, destroying aesthetic beauty of the environment among others. This findings agrees with that of Ohaka, Ozor and Ohaka (2013) who recorded that the effects of poor waste disposal practices are the main cause of environmental pollution, disease outbreak, blocking of gutters, and reduction in aesthetic beauty of the environment. Ghana Environmental Agency (2010) reported that sanitary condition resulting from poor waste disposal practices causes health problems such as malaria, diarrhea, and cholera among others.

Table 4 shows sustainable practices for efficient clothing articles waste disposal. These practices include buying only clothing articles needed, reusing, repairing, refashioning, repurposing, recycling clothing articles, renting clothes, avoiding impulsive buying, burning, burying and throwing away clothing articles. This study agrees with that of Aydin (2017) who noted that consumers bring out their worn out clothing article into reuse by selling, donating, giving away to friends and for recycling as sustainable practices for efficient clothing article waste

disposal. In the same vein, Dissanayak, Perera and Wanniarachch (2017) revealed that reuse, recycling and refashioning as waste management strategy.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The predominance of post-consumer waste has resulted to generation of large volume of textile waste daily. During waste disposal, money is wasted and disposal methods if not sustainable could result to public health hazards. Achieving sustainability with respect to textile and apparel goods is a complex issue that does not just end with the sale of goods to consumers. The disposition of clothing is an integral aspect of the clothing consumption process. Therefore, the need for sustainable clothing waste disposal practices. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made

1. Sustainable clothing article waste disposal practices should be adopted by households in Port Harcourt metropolis.
2. Consumers should buy more durable clothing articles and extend the life through reuse.
3. Stake holders and government should collaborate and set up clothing recycling plant in Port Harcourt.
4. Consumers should have positive attitudes toward the environment.

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